

Scientific article

Steady-state evaluation of fatigue loads for the helix wake-mixing control method

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Published on: Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Volume 3224, Proceedings of TORQUE 2026, Bruges (3–5 June 2026)

Abstract: *Wake-mixing strategies offer promising opportunities to increase wind farm power production, but their impact on structural fatigue loading remains insufficiently understood. This study evaluates the helix wake-mixing method by jointly assessing power gains and fatigue loads at the wind-farm scale. A steady-state helix wake model is coupled to a data-driven load surrogate model. The surrogate model was trained on aeroelastic simulations using inflow slices generated by large-eddy simulations and predicts damage equivalent loads based on sector-averaged wind speed and turbulence intensity. The coupled framework is first evaluated on a two-turbine array, considering varying helix pitch amplitudes and wake overlap. The model captures the trends observed when coupling the surrogate model to large-eddy simulation inflow, showing increased fatigue loads on both upstream and downstream turbines. The framework is subsequently applied to a 69-turbine offshore wind farm case study. Farm-wide optimization of the helix method at below-rated wind speeds yields an increase of up to 1.1 % in annual energy production, accompanied by increased fatigue loading across all evaluated components. The largest increases are observed for the pitch bearings, while tower base loads are less affected.*

Link to article: <https://iopscience.iop.org/volume/1742-6596/3224>

SUDOCO is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101122256). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.